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SCHOOL MANAGER: MOTIVATIONAL AGENT

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ABSTRACT

Education is one of the main foundations of society. Therefore, one can imagine the great responsibility involved in tasks related to school management and its role in addressing existing diversity. It encompasses a vast field of information and activities, which must be carefully analyzed to discover the best way to manage all these school processes. After all, there is more involved than just teaching itself. The proper functioning of the entire school environment should ensure that members of the academic community are always well-supported in their practices. Therefore, the concept of school management and how it works is presented; its pillars, its criteria, and how it is possible to assist all segments of the school and guide them towards the need for an environment that promotes and respects cultural plurality.

Keywords: School management. Educational leadership. Motivation in the school environment. Cultural diversity.